

Perception of New Indian Women in the Novels of Nayantara Sahgal

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Abstract

Nayantara Sahgal was born on May 10, 1927, to Ranjit Sitaram Pandit and Vijayalakshmi Pandit as the second of their three daughters. She has issued eight novels, two autobiographies and a political reading of Indira Gandhi's years in authority along with a significant number of journalistic writings mostly on contemporary political events and a lot of women, giving a clarion call to women to appear as a 'new women' journeying towards freedom. This article focuses on the idea of New Indian Women in her novels. The notion of 'New Women' with a "new morality" based on reason and justice is of current origin, struggling to cultivate into any reasonable form. This article gives a complete appraisal of the highlights of the problems, especially of women.

Keywords: chastity, morality, freedom, marriage, chauvinism.

Nayantara Sahgal is one of the eminent Indo English writers who inscribe in the tributary & national consciousness. She is a prolific writer and her literary norm of nine novels, two autobiographies and some non-fictional works. Nayantara Sahgal has introduced a large number of autobiographical elements in her books. For a query, she asserts that 'all art is autobiographical' (Women's Space the Mosaic World of Margaret Drabble and Nayantara Sahgal, 27). Her work ranges from honest and emotional autobiography to fictionalized autobiography.

Nayantara believes that it is not a severe, moral offense in a woman to break away from the 'sacred' marriage bond if she finds the shackles too harsh to the enlargement of her inner self. She finds that a women's responsibility to be genuine to her inner self is far superior and critical than to be for family and society. Nayantara portrays the unchallengeable right of freedom in women in many of the characters in her novels, such as Simrit, Saroj, and Rashmi. This piece of writing focuses on the perception of New Indian Woman in India through the ages so that it might throw brightness on the approach and action of those problems by Nayantara Sahgal.

Through centuries the perception of perfect womanhood has been based on mythological personages like Sita, Nalayani. A woman was supposed to be under the concern of a male throughout her life. One part made a great crash is that which disallows any autonomy for women, is as follows:

Pitaarakshatikaumaree, bhartharakshatiyauvanee

Putroorakshativardhakyee, nastri

Swathantharyamarhati (ix,3) (Women and her family, 2)

(‘The father protects the woman during childhood, the husband during her youth and the son during her old age. A woman does not deserve freedom’).

A woman is therefore inculcated with the ideals of martyrdom, of satisfaction intolerance, of the need to believe a lower status through the mythological models of Sita, Savithri, Gandhari, etc.

The dialogue between Rose and Ram in the novel ‘The Rich Like Us’ is introduced to carry to light the circumstance of women usually prevailing in Society. Another vice perpetrated in society is the male privilege over female issues. Women are considered as commodities, more significant the convenience. Men do not worry about the poignant constraints, which they require upon women. Women have to put up with such inconveniences on financial considerations. When Ram represents Draupdi was gambled away by her five husbands, Rose is accurately shocked.

Sahgal approaches the trouble of women with liability, ripeness, and understanding. She is conscious of the fact that women’s problems are not confined to women only. Society consists of men and women, and the pleasure of one or the other depends upon a co-operative endeavor. Women cannot be aggressive towards men as they cannot be so without danger. The accountability of bringing about a joyful society rests uniformly on men and women in society. Sahgal understands the requirements for strength of co-operation on the piece of men. It is the responsibility of the educated, dependable men in society to assist in the liberation of women. Sahgal brings out this point obviously when she makes her heroines in the novels needy on the trustworthy men in society. Simrit is maintained and guided by Raj in every way. It is Raj who tries to fracture the strength of submissiveness in Simrit and construct her to obtain some positive action. Under his power, inconsistently she says that she feels entirely free.

It is Dubey who directs and supports Saroj to create her imagine liberally, to break away from the shackles, particularly if they establish worthless or indefensible. Rashmi is directed by Kalidas. It seems that Sahgal makes her heroines intentionally submissive or reliant so that responsible men should come advance to assist them discover their way in the mire. It is the society’s dependability, Sahgal believes, to get steps to progress the excellence of existence for women, to create them full-fledged human beings, to understand their self-governing ‘personhood.’

Society consists of men and women. She cautions woman not to squander away their rigid on freedom in fighting for impartiality in costume or performance. They should attain something substantial to show their advantage. A self-fulfilled woman will be a benefit to the family. She also finds responsibility with the society, which observes a dual standard with perceive to virtue or morality. While culture imposes sturdy sanctions against even slight indiscretions on the element of women, it shows significant compassion towards such aberrations in men. She also castigated the undue importance given to moderation. The perception of morality, according to Sahgal, is much more related to intelligence than to corpse. Most of the times the penalty falls heavy on the aggrieved party that is related to woman. For her, Sex is not an operator of the body or for the movement, but it permeates mind and power and all activities of husband and wife. It is a perform of the finale of love, understanding of kindness. But it does not mean she is for promiscuity. She condemns the perkiness and excesses in sex in women as exemplified in her novels.

This critique was undertaken a critical study of the novels of Nayantara Sahgal in an endeavor to appear at some suitable conclusions regarding her attitude towards women's problems and how she envisages "the perception of new women in India."

In Sahgal's *Storm in Chandigarh* Inder, the husband, who himself is hankering following another woman Mara, frequently rebukes and harasses his wife Saroj because of her past sexual pleasure with her college mate once; Ram in *Rich Like Us* has previously two wives at home, but he continues to expand adoring love activities with Marcela. Sahgal feels, "if chastity is so important and so well worth preserving. It would be easier to safeguard it by keeping men seclusion, not women." (*Chandigarh* 191)

Marriage is sincere as well as the difficulty of all human relations. Religion considers marriage as a sacred union of two souls. But the similar religion imposes stiff code of behavior for women. Wounded butterflies who stretched to live to emerge out of chrysalis and find an opening in doing social service as in the case of Maya in *A Time to be Morning*; Rashmi terminations her marriage and stands unaccompanied in *This Time of Morning*; Simrit, a freelancer, marries Raj starts a fresh life in the *Day in shadow*: Saroj an innocent and caring mother bravely comes and discover consolation in Vishal in *Storm in Chandigarh*; and Devi, a woman cabinet minister, survives without help in politics in *A Situation in New Delhi*.

There are female characters that, in the name of freedom, irritated the limits of family and marriage. In Sahgal's *A Time to be Happy*, Lalitha Chatterjee, a very significant person, drinks and has an affair with an additional man: Uma Mitra, the young wife of Arjun Mitra, smokes, flirts, drinks, and ruins herself: and Leela, as student, conceives out of marriage commits suicide when she sees of it in *This Time of Morning*, Gauri, freely has sex with Vishal in the lack of her husband, Nikhil: Leela, the disloyal wife of Vishal, dies, when her pregnancy is medically finished: and Mara has a special affair with Inder outwardly the facts of *Jit in Storm in Chandigarh*. This breach of ethics in their existence does not permit them to become new women. Sahgal looks to have a clear message to convey when women resort to dissolution their life becomes either worthless or end up in an abnormal death. Sahgal's marital ethics, as revealed in her works, is based on sincerity, mutual faith, considerations, understanding, and liberty; she attacks egotism, pretense, which result consequently in marital breakdown.

Instinctively, her major women characters stay agreeable, student, quiet and suffering, but when faced with discrimination Maya, Saroj, Rashmi or Simrit, they explain the sight of awaking, discard the stereotype and speak out the fact. Earlier they have been only humans' obedient and conforming persons, but later on, they are sovereign and whole beings.

Men like Inder in *Storm in Chandigarh*, Som in *The Day in Shadow* are the personification of Chauvinism. They have the code of behavior as far as they are worried and an additional where women are concerned. As a consequence, Saroj and Simrit suffer embarrassment and pain. But they administer to live on once they come out of their marriages, from 'the subdued sex, creatures not yet emerged from the chrysalis.' (*Chandigarh* 189) they were 'filled with the sheer rightness of beings alive and healthy.' (*Shadow* 236)

The regular communication Sahgal gives is men and women are equals, and nonviolent survival depends on common respect and understanding, women should have the ethical bravery to maintain the rights and 'men..were born to lead and sometimes educate to triumph'. (*Shadow* 236).

Works Cited

1. Beauvoir, de Simone. *The Second Sex* (Trans.H.M.Parsley : 1949). Harmonds Worth: Penguin, 1970. Print.
2. Deshpande, Y.P. *Indian Novelists in English*. Jaipur :Vital Publications, 2011. Print.

3. Iyengar, K.R.Srinivas. Indian Writing in English. New Delhi : Sterling, 1982. Print.
4. Manohar, Lal. Modern English Literature. Delhi: Swastik Publications, 1993. Print.
5. Sahgal, Nayantara. A Time to be Happy. New Delhi: Sterling Publishes, 1975. Print.
6. Sahgal, Nayantara. The Day in Shadow. New Delhi: Hind Pocket Books, 1975. Print.
7. Sahgal, Nayantara. Storm in Chandigarh. New Delhi: Hind Pocket Books, 1970. Print.